

The Antecedents and Outcomes of Brand Relationship Quality and Customer Engagement

Andam Jamal

Abstract:

Nowadays, hotels need further efforts to grow new streams of income as rivalry is penetrating and new visitors are difficult to confirm at a mature phrase. It is vital for hotel managers to recognize additional concerning customer engagement with brand, to recognize what the antecedents of these kind of engagements are, and to distinguish what consequences they are able to achieve from customer engagement. The study aimed to investigate the background and result of brand relationship quality and customer engagement at hotels industry in the Northern of Iraq. Quantitative Research used in the current study. Quantitative Research is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results to a larger population. According to the ministry of tourism, 3 million people visited Erbil on 2018. the authors have used online sample calculator to measure my sample size, according to that I have found that the authors need to distribute 400 questionnaires, but the authors received 353 valid questionnaires. The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure research hypotheses, the findings revealed that the highest value and most effective concerning measuring the background and result of brand relationship quality and customer engagement at hotels industry in the Northern of Iraq, was first hypothesis which stated that Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality. In contrast, the lowest value was for second hypothesis which stated that Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement.

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1. Introduction

Hospitality and tourism industry have understood development in economies over the past decade. Hospitality and tourism industry have become the main economic persuader in generating occupations and investment chances. The hotel is the main service industry in the tourism and hospitality.

Service marketing experts and service brands have lately revealed concentration in Brand relationship quality, particularly in hotel industry (Seetana et al. 2020). Service marketing experts have come to understand that recognizing how hotel visitors contribute and engage with brands is significant when emerging combined brand relationship quality and customer engagement for the purpose of creating sensitive promises, for instance excellent brand involvements, brand loyalty, and brand satisfaction (Xiao et al. 2019).

BRQ could be established in various methods. Service hotels could concentrate on emerging satisfaction and trust as key features of relationship quality—two extremely significant concepts provided a service brand's danger for unpredictable outcome and the connected high stage of supposed uncertainty by hotel visitors (Zhang and Cobanoglu, 2019). Yet, hotels could correspondingly shape an effective emotional link with visitors. According to Qiu et al. (2019) "the achievement of hotels determines the detail that hotels shaped and created an emotional link with their visitors. Since, on the daily basis hotels deal with visitors directly. Hotels' products are not the same as other industries, customers can see and touch the product then decide and make a judgment, in contrast; hotels need to build an emotional and feeling attachment with their visitors. The significance of visitors' feeling have been revealed in studies on service encounters, service marketing, and replies to service disappointments (Koc, 2019). Therefore, on top of the well-organized key features of connection quality (for instance, trust, positive feeling, engagement and satisfaction), feelings can have a main role in creating an effective and deep visitors-brand relationships (Wijayati & Suryaputra, 2020).

The perception of customer engagement (CE) developed early 2006 as a part of the engagement that required to examine the buyers' attitudes and behavior toward the connections/contribution with brands (Mathew and Sreejesh, 2017). Buyers could create value to businesses by several methods beside than transaction process (Woo et al. 2018). Lately, non-transactional buyer behavior has become a main thought (Su et al. 2018). Consequently, discovery substitute approaches by which to shape and create associations, engage buyers by providing and offering an excellent service to visitors in order to gain competitive advantage at hotel industries (Arsedi & Li, 2020). Though, engaging visitors dependably and properly is a ongoing challenge for hotels that provide an excellent services to its visitors (Joseph, 2019). In the hospitality industry, many studies concentrate on the effect of brand relationship quality on visitors' engagement. The hospitality and tourism studies broadly sustenance the possible advantage of CE. For instance, visitors' review on their certain stay at a particular hotel will have a positive and significant influence on the perception of visitors' engagement and attracting more visitors, eventually gaining competitive advantage over other hotels in the industry, additional visitors' acknowledgements of service quality (Peters et al. 2019). Furthermore, leveraging CE emotion can permit hotels to sustain and attract additional visitors/travelers (Xiong and King, 2019). Current study proposes that engaging travelers post trip can enable travelers become supporters and promoters for the journey by using word of mouth with other protentional visitors (Aluri et al. 2019).

1.1 Conceptual framework

Fig. 1- Research Model

- H1a: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality.
- H1b: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement.
- H2a: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality.
- H2b: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement.
- H3a: Brand relationship quality is positively related to re-purchase intention.
- H3b: Brand relationship quality is positively related to word of mouth.
- H4a: Customer engagement is positively related to word of mouth.
- H4b: Customer engagement is positively related to Re-purchase intention.
- H5a: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth.
- H5b: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention.
- H6a: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention.
- H6b: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth.
- H7a: BRQ mediates HRB and word of mouth.
- H7b: BRQ mediates HRB and re-purchase intentions
- H8a: Customer engagement mediates HRB and word of mouth.
- H8a: Customer engagement mediates HRB and re-purchase intention

2. Literature review

2.1 The concept of Quality

Nowadays quality is the consequence of developing and gradually varied requirements of the customers, along with an extremely growing rivalry and the growth of contemporary technology. Managing quality means continuously following excellence: confirm that the business suits for aim, and not just remain in the same level, but rather than aiming in enhancement and development (Sürücü et al. 2019). According to Huang et al. (2019), quality is a simple instrument for a normal belonging of service or product that permits it to be linked with another service or product in the same industry or line of products. Additionally, the quality of service or product is the awareness that buyers have about that service or product. It is a customer's mind-set who receives a precise service or product and recognizes its capability to meet customers' expectations and needs.

2.2 Service Quality

Service quality is the of the greatest successful factors of buyers' needs and requirements. It aids organizations for instance hotels growing their market and creating vast buyers' section. Additionally, it empowers hotels enhancing their reputation and image. Service quality is the chief pointers of income and buyers' gratification (Martínez and Nishiyama, 2019). Moreover, it is essential that hotels should take into their consideration that service quality is an important method of maintainable competitive advantage, as it influences the continuous enhancement of service outcome by growing market share and income development (Haque, et al. 2018). Moreover, Sarker et al. (2019), claims that service quality could be defined as the consequence from buyer judgements between their outlooks concerning the service they will utilize and their insights concerning the service hotel. The quality of service in hotel is a significant feature of effective hotel. The current tendency of whole quality in hotel confirms the attainment of competitive advantage of hotel and is consequently the theme of modern study into service quality in hotel industry. Ou et al. (2020) defined service as 'an achievement or a movement which could be provided by a group to another group, which is essentially intangible and cannot influence any proprietorship. Service can be associated to tangible product or intangible product. Service quality is commonly observed as the result of the service distribution scheme, particularly in the circumstance of unadulterated service schemes. Furthermore, service quality is associated to buyer satisfaction. Buyers, though, form views concerning service quality not only from a sole source nonetheless from a host of participating influences (Xu and Wang, 2020).

2.3 Brand Relationship Quality

Branding as a message approach is to progress perceived variances among rival presents in a customers' concentration and it can be done through a long-run statement procedure containing of diverse phases that participate to brand justice for customers (Rather, 2020). In a service framework, the brand is caused from purchaser involvements and knowledge during the service come across (Lei et al. 2020). This brand message procedure includes one-way and two-way means functioning at the business, advertising and marketing announcement stages. A buyer-brand association is a concept that distinguishes the interactivity between a brand and its customers (Tsai et al. 2020). Workers' behaviors, customer contribution and their communications in a service are significant fundamentals for customer satisfaction (Chen et al. 2020). The regular communications between customers and their service providers generate unique brand knowledges that distinguish from rival presents (Gruss et al. 2020). Furthermore, it is recognized as brand communication, which is the association that customers, feel, think and have with a certain service or product brand. Brand academics usually evaluate the way that customers observe and assess brands

investigative brand behaviour, brand assessments, or supposed brand excellence (Prentice et al. 2020). Lately, scholars stated that customers vary not just in brand awareness, nonetheless similarly the way that customers link to brands (Albayrak et al. 2020). For instance, customers frequently do not differentiate between brands and brand producers. Additional, venders regularly determine to persuade customers to reflect and believe of their brands as an existing by retaining image, and anthropomorphosis also utilizing individuals' attributes and behavior (Papen et al. 2020). Brand relations with an individual qualities result in developing epitomal and positive feeling involvement and customers define their associations with brands in community association (Han and Lee, 2020). The association between consumers and brand is an exclusive and different one that could have significant results for both sides. Buyers grow associations with brands and believe of them as associates (Banton & Daniel, 2018).

2.4 Loyalty program

Loyalty is somewhat that all businesses would seek to merely by asset of their being. Loyalty programs inspire customers to repurchase from the same place. Several of the inducements can comprise advanced entree to modern service or products, further promotions or occasionally free product. Consumers characteristically enroll their individual info with the business and are provided a different promotions and loyalty program, for instance, membership, telephone number or ID number and utilize that identity at the time they are purchasing product or service from the same business (Martínez and Nishiyama, 2019).

A loyalty program is an approach used by businesses for the purpose of marketing, which is intended to inspire buyers to return and consciously purchase from the same place. Nowadays, these kinds of plans cover greatest sorts of business, each these plans have different types of incentive and bonus plan, loyalty program mostly used in hospitality industry and particularly in hotels (Ou et al. 2020).

2.5 Customer Engagement

The perception of the customer engagement covers in "extended area of association marketing." (Su et al. 2018). Correspondingly, Joseph, (2019) propose that to study customer engagement, wider perception of association marketing philosophy is suitable. During this extend area of association marketing, business's concentrate on emerging association with both potential and current purchasers, also business value formation systems and customer societies. As such, precise communicating customer experiences define the chief centric idea of customer engagement. According to the above-mentioned investigations and studies, Peters et al. (2019) assume that inside marketing scheme customer engagement is a significant thought. Perception of engagement defined by Xiong and King, (2019) as psychological and emotional act of communication of customers with business, brand, further customers and societies. Prentice et al. (2020) similarly propose that performance of "engaging" aid purchasers to generate value by their collaborating involvements with businesses and other buyers (Kalu & Enyia, 2019).

3. Methodology

Quantitative Research used in the current study. Quantitative Research is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results to a larger population. According to the ministry of tourism, 3 million people visited Erbil on 2018. The authors have used online sample calculator to measure my sample size, according to that the authors have found that the authors need to distribute 400 questionnaires, but the authors received 353 valid questionnaires.

4. Analysis

4.1 Demographic Analysis

Table 1-Demographic analysis

No	Items	Scales	Frequency	Percent
1	Gender	Male	228	64.6
		Female	125	35.4
2	Age	20-29	44	12.5
		30-39	86	24.4
		40-49	100	28.3
		50-59	96	27.2
		60-69	27	7.6
3	Education	High school	10	2.8
		Diploma	38	10.8
		Bachelor	168	47.6
		Master	93	26.3
		PhD	32	9.1
		Other	12	3.4
4	Purpose of visit	Leisure	168	47.6
		Business	185	52.4

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

Table (1) demonstrates the visitors' background information contributed in the current study, the findings revealed that 228 male visitors contributed in the current study on the other hand 125 female visitors, however the results showed that the majority of male visitors contributed in this study. Concerning visitors' education, the findings showed that 10 visitors had high school certificate, 38 visitors had Diploma certificate, 168 visitors had bachelor's degree, 93 visitors had master's degree, 32 visitors had PhD degree and 12 visitors had other degree than listed above. As for the purpose of visitors' visiting hotels; it was found that 168 visitors' purpose of their visit was leisure and 185 visitors' purpose of their visit was business.

4.2 Reliability analysis

Table 2-Reliability analysis

No	Variables	No of items	Cronbach alpha
1	Hotel stay related membership benefits	.791	9
2	Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits	.765	3
3	Brand relationship quality	.746	9
4	Customer engagement	.756	4
5	Word of mouth	.743	7
6	Re-purchase intention	.736	5

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

For the purpose of items reliability, the authors applied reliability statistics to measure the reliabilities, however the findings revealed that the Cronbach alpha's value for HBR was .791 for nine questions, the Cronbach alpha's value for NHBR was .765 for three questions, the Cronbach alpha's value for BRQ was .746 for nine questions, the Cronbach alpha's value for CE was .756 for four questions, the Cronbach alpha's value for WOM was .743 for seven questions, and the Cronbach alpha's value for REI was .736 for five questions, however the findings showed that all variables and questions used to measure this study were reliable since all Cronbach alpha's value were higher than 0.7.

4.3 Results

The analysis shown below consists of two sections; first section consists of six research hypotheses measurement by applying a simple regression analysis, and the second section consists of two last research hypotheses (7&8) by applying Sobel test to measure the mediation analysis between variables.

H1a: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality.

Table 3-Correlations- Hypothesis 1a- (HRB &BRQ)

Correlations			
		HRB	BRQ
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.709**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	352	352
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	.709**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	352	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and BRQ, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .709** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and BRQ.

Table 4- Coefficients- Hypothesis 1a- (HRB &BRQ)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.487	.188		2.584	.010
	BRQ	.905	.048	.709	18.785	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HRB

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure first hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality). The value B was found to be (.905) which is higher than .005 with P value of .000, indicated that the first hypothesis (a) was supported.

H1b: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement.

Table 5- Correlation-Hypothesis 1b-(HRB&CE)

Correlations			
		HRB	CE
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	352	352
CE	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	352	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and CE, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .470** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and CE.

Table 6- Coefficients Hypothesis-1b-(HRB&CE)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.555	.148		17.250	.000
	CE	.379	.038	.470	9.949	.000
a. Dependent Variable: HRB						

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure first hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement). The value B was found to be (.379) which is higher than .005 with P value of .000, indicated that the first hypothesis (b) was supported.

H2a: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality.

Table 7- Correlation- Hypothesis 2a-(NHRB&CE)

Correlations			
		NONHRB	BRQ
NONHRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.217**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	.217**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between NHRB and BRQ, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .217** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between NHRB and BRQ.

Table 8- Coefficients- Hypothesis 2a-(NHRB&CE)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.090	.290		10.664	.000
	HRB	.223	.072	.164	3.111	.002
a. Dependent Variable: NONHRB						

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure second hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality). The value B was found to be (.223) which is higher than .005 with P value of .000, indicated that the second hypothesis (a) was supported.

H2b: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement.

Table 9- Correlation- Hypothesis 2b-(NHRB&CE)

Correlations				
		NONHRB		CE
NONHRB	Pearson Correlation	1		.175**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.001
	N	353		353
CE	Pearson Correlation	.175**		1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		
	N	353		353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between NHRB and CE, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .175** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between NHRB and CE.

Table 10- Coefficients- Hypothesis 2b-(NHRB&CE)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.241	.225		14.399	.000
	CE	.193	.058	.175	3.329	.001

a. Dependent Variable: NONHRB

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure second hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement). The value B was found to be (.193) which is higher than .005 with P value of .000, indicated that the second hypothesis (b) was supported.

H3a: Brand relationship quality is positively related to re-purchase intention.

Table 11- Correlation- Hypothesis 3a-(BRQ&REI)

Correlations				
		BRQ		REI
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	1		.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000
	N	353		353
REI	Pearson Correlation	.589**		1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	353		353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between BRQ and REI, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .589** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between BRQ and REI.

Table 12- Coefficients- Hypothesis 3a- (BRQ&REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.137	.207		5.481	.000
	BRQ	.724	.053	.589	13.661	.000

a. Dependent Variable: REI

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure third hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Brand relationship quality is positively related to re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.724) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the third hypothesis (a) was supported.

H3b: Brand relationship quality is positively related to word of mouth.

Table 13- Correlation- Hypothesis 3b-(BRQ&WOM)

Correlations			
		BRQ	WOM
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	1	.476**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
WOM	Pearson Correlation	.476**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between BRQ and WOM, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .476** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between BRQ and WOM.

Table 14- Coefficients- Hypothesis 3b-(BRQ&WOM)

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.268	.265		4.794	.000
BRQ	.687	.068	.476	10.153	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WOM

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure third hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Brand relationship quality is positively related to word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.687) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the third hypothesis (b) was supported.

H4a: Customer engagement is positively related to word of mouth.

Table 15- Correlation- Hypothesis 4a-(CE&WOM)

Correlations			
		CE	WOM
CE	Pearson Correlation	1	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
WOM	Pearson Correlation	.623**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between CE and WOM, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .623** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between CE and WOM.

Table 16- Coefficients- Hypothesis 4a-(CE&WOM)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.761	.148		11.921	.000
	CE	.567	.038	.623	14.934	.000
a. Dependent Variable: WOM						

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure fourth hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Customer engagement is positively related to word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.567) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the fourth hypothesis (a) was supported.

H4b: Customer engagement is positively related to Re-purchase intention.

Table 17- Correlation- Hypothesis 4b-(CE&REP)

Correlations			
		CE	REI
CE	Pearson Correlation	1	.730**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
REI	Pearson Correlation	.730**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between CE and REI, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .730** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between CE and REI.

Table 18- Coefficients - Hypothesis 4b-(CE& REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.777	.110		16.148	.000
	CE	.567	.028	.730	20.035	.000
a. Dependent Variable: REI						

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure fourth hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Customer engagement is positively related to Re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.567) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the fourth hypothesis (b) was supported.

H5a: Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth.

Table 19- Correlation - Hypothesis 5a-(HRB&WOM)

Correlations			
		HRB	WOM
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.409**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	352	352
WOM	Pearson Correlation	.409**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	352	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and WOM, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .409** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and WOM.

Table 20- Coefficients - Hypothesis 5a-(HRB&WOM)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.090	.222		9.408	.000
	HRB	.462	.055	.409	8.395	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WOM

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure fifth hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.462) which is higher than .005 with P value of .000, indicated that the fifth hypothesis (a) was supported

Table 21- Correlation - Hypothesis 5b- (HRB& REI)

Correlations			
		HRB	REI
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.533**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	352	352
REI	Pearson Correlation	.533**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	352	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and REI, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .533** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and REI.

Table 22- Coefficients - Hypothesis 5b- (HRB& REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.904	.176		10.840	.000
	HRB	.512	.043	.533	11.784	.000

a. Dependent Variable: REI

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure fifth hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.512) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the fifth hypothesis (b) was supported.

H6a: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention.

Table 23- Correlation - Hypothesis 6a- (NHRB& REI)

Correlations			
		NONHRB	REI
NONHRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.502**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
REI	Pearson Correlation	.502**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between NHRB and REI, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .502** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between NHRB and REI.

Table 24- Coefficients - Hypothesis 6a-(NHRB& REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.550	.131		19.461	.000
	NONHRB	.354	.033	.502	10.885	.000

a. Dependent Variable: REI

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure sixth hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.354) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the sixth hypothesis (a) was supported.

H6b: Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth.

Table 25- Correlation - Hypothesis 6b-(NHRB&WOM)

Correlations			
		NONHRB	WOM
NONHRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.517**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	353	353
WOM	Pearson Correlation	.517**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between NHRB and WOM, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .517** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between NHRB and WOM.

Table 26- Coefficients - Hypothesis 6b-(NHRB&WOM)

Model		Coefficients				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.243	.152		14.754	.000
	NONHRB	.427	.038	.517	11.314	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WOM

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure sixth hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.427) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the sixth hypothesis (b) was supported.

4.4 Mediation Analysis

H7a: BRQ mediates HRB and word of mouth

Table 27- Correlation - Hypothesis 7a- (HRB, BRQ, WOM)

		Correlations		
		WOM	HRB	BRQ
WOM	Pearson Correlation	1	.409**	.476**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	353	352	353
HRB	Pearson Correlation	.409**	1	.709**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	352	352	352
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	.476**	.709**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	353	352	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between WOM and HRB, WOM and BRQ, BRQ and HRB, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .409** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between WOM and HRB. Moreover, the value of correlation is .476** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between WOM and BRQ, and the value of correlation is .709** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between BRQ and HRB.

Table 28- Coefficients - Hypothesis 7a- (HRB, BRQ, WOM)

Model		Coefficients			t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.670	.119		14.007	.000
	HRB	.555	.030	.709	18.785	.000

a. Dependent Variable: BRQ

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure seventh hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (BRQ mediates HRB and word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.555) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the seventh hypothesis (a) was supported.

Table 29- Coefficients - Hypothesis 7a- (HRB, BRQ, WOM)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.268	.265		4.794	.000
	BRQ	.687	.068	.476	10.153	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WOM

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure seventh hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (BRQ mediates HRB and word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.687) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the seventh hypothesis (a) was supported.

Table 30- Sobel Test - Hypothesis 7a- (HRB, BRQ, WOM)

Input:	Test statistic	Std. Error:	p-value:
a .555	Sobel test: 8.86690	0.0430093	0
b .687	Aroian test: 8.85694	0.04304929	0
s _a .030	Goodman test: 8.87689687	0.04295251	0
s _b .068	Reset all	Calculate	

H7b: BRQ mediates HRB and re-purchase intentions

Table 31- Correlation - Hypothesis 7b- (HRB, BRQ, REI)

Correlations				
		HRB	BRQ	REI
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.709**	.533**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	352	352	352
BRQ	Pearson Correlation	.709**	1	.589**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	352	353	353
REI	Pearson Correlation	.533**	.589**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	352	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and BRQ, HRB and REI, REI and BRQ, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .709** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and BRQ. Moreover, the value of correlation is .533** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and REI, and the value of correlation is .589** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between REI and BRQ.

Table 32- Coefficient - Hypothesis 7b- (HRB, BRQ, REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.487	.188		2.584	.010
	BRQ	.905	.048	.709	18.785	.000

a. Dependent Variable: HRB

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure seventh hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (BRQ mediates HRB and re-purchase intentions). The value B was found to be (.905) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the seventh hypothesis (b) was supported.

Table 33- Coefficient - Hypothesis 7b- (HRB, BRQ, REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.904	.176		10.840	.000
	HRB	.512	.043	.533	11.784	.000

a. Dependent Variable: RP

Table 34- Sobel Test - Hypothesis 7b- (HRB, BRQ, REP)

Input:		Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a	.905	Sobel test: 10.06743801	0.04602561	0
b	.512	Aroian test: 10.05733025	0.04607187	0
s _a	.048	Goodman test: 10.0775763	0.04597931	0
s _b	.043	Reset all	Calculate	

H8a: Customer engagement mediates HRB and word of mouth.

Table 34- Correlation- Hypothesis 8a- (HRB, CE, WOM)

Correlations					
		HRB	CE	WOM	
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**	.409**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	
	N	352	352	352	
CE	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1	.623**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	
	N	352	353	353	
WOM	Pearson Correlation	.409**	.623**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	352	353	353	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and CE, HRB and WOM, CE and WOM, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .470** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and CE. Moreover, the value of correlation is .409** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and WOM, and the value of correlation is .623** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between CE and WOM.

Table 35- coefficient - Hypothesis 8a- (HRB, CE, WOM)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.515	.236		6.415	.000
	HRB	.582	.058	.470	9.949	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CE

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure eighth hypothesis(a) which demonstrated that (Customer engagement mediates HRB and word of mouth). The value B was found to be (.582) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the eighth hypothesis (a) was supported.

Table 36- coefficients - Hypothesis 8a- (HRB, CE, WOM)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.761	.148		11.921	.000
	CE	.567	.038	.623	14.934	.000

a. Dependent Variable: WOM

Table 37- Sobel Test - Hypothesis 8a- (HRB, CE, WOM)

Input:		Test statistic:		Std. Error:	p-value:
a	.582	Sobel test:	8.32668921	0.03963088	0
b	.567	Aroian test:	8.31384249	0.03969212	0
s _a	.058	Goodman test:	8.33959566	0.03956954	0
s _b	.038	Reset all		Calculate	

H8a: Customer engagement mediates HRB and re-purchase intention

Table 38- Sobel Test - Hypothesis 8b- (HRB, CE, REI)

Correlations				
		HRB	CE	REI
HRB	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**	.533**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	352	352	352
CE	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1	.730**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	352	353	353
REI	Pearson Correlation	.533**	.730**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	352	353	353

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The above table demonstrates the correlation between HRB and CE, HRB and REI, CE and REI, as it can be seen that the value of correlation is .470** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and CE. Moreover, the value of correlation is .533** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between HRB and REI, and the value of correlation is .730** this proves that there is a positive and significant correlation between CE and REI.

Table 39- Coefficients - Hypothesis 8b- (HRB, CE, REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.515	.236		6.415	.000
	HRB	.582	.058	.470	9.949	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CE

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure eighth hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Customer engagement mediates HRB and re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.582) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the eighth hypothesis (b) was supported.

Table 40- Coefficients - Hypothesis 8b- (HRB, CE, REI)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.777	.110		16.148	.000
	CE	.567	.028	.730	20.035	.000

a. Dependent Variable: RP

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure eighth hypothesis(b) which demonstrated that (Customer engagement mediates HRB and re-purchase intention). The value B was found to be (.567) which is higher than.005 with P value of .000, indicated that the eighth hypothesis (b) was supported.

Table 41- Sobel Test - Hypothesis 8b- (HRB, CE, REI)

Input:	Test statistic:	Std. Error:	p-value:
a .582	Sobel test: 8.99113274	0.03670216	0
b .567	Aroian test: 8.9823438	0.03673807	0
s _a .058	Goodman test: 8.99994752	0.03666621	0
s _b .028	Reset all	Calculate	

Source: (SPSS, By author, 2020)

5. Conclusion

Hotels' service quality of in the contemporary hotel business is influenced by an extensive variety of influences, nonetheless the utmost significant features are inspired and happy individuals. Inadequately expert and dissatisfied hotel staffs could have long run negative

influence on the hotels' service quality. The hotel should be directed by a mission to gain more effective human resource, for instance, employees educational background, customer service, customer satisfaction, customer engagement and brand quality offered by hotel. The study aimed to investigate the background and result of brand relationship quality and customer engagement at hotels industry in the Northern of Iraq. The authors applied a simple regression analysis to measure research hypotheses that developed earlier as it can be seen in figure (1), the findings revealed that the highest value and most effective concerning measuring the background and result of brand relationship quality and customer engagement at hotels industry in the Northern of Iraq, was first hypothesis which stated that Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality. In contrast, the lowest value was for second hypothesis (b) which stated that Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement. Moreover, the study found that Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence customer engagement, Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence Brand relationship quality, Brand relationship quality is positively related to re-purchase intention, Brand relationship quality is positively related to word of mouth, Customer engagement is positively related to word of mouth, Customer engagement is positively related to Re-purchase intention, Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth, Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention, Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence re-purchase intention, Non-Hotel stay related membership benefits of loyalty program positively influence word of mouth, BRQ mediates HRB and word of mouth, BRQ mediates HRB and re-purchase intentions, Customer engagement mediates HRB and word of mouth, and finally Customer engagement mediates HRB and re-purchase intention

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